

CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY TOWARDS THE WORKERS IN TEA INDUSTRY OF ASSAM – A CASE STUDY WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO THREE COMPANY BASED INDUSTRY

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Abstract:

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) defined as “the ethical behavior of a company towards the society,” manifests itself in the form of such noble programs initiated by for-profit organizations. CSR has become increasingly prominent in the Indian corporate scenario because organizations have realized that besides growing their businesses, it is also vital to build trustworthy and sustainable relationships with the community at large. This is one of the key drivers of CSR programs. Though India is one of the fastest growing economies, socio-economic problems like poverty, illiteracy, lack of healthcare etc. are still ubiquitous and the government has limited resources to tackle these challenges. This scenario has opened up several areas for businesses to contribute towards social development. Companies have CSR teams that devise specific policies, strategies and goals for their CSR programs and set aside budgets to support them. Corporate Social Responsibility means the way in which business firms integrate environmental, economic and social concerns into their culture, values, strategy, decision making and operations in an accountable and transparent manner and therefore, leading to better creation of wealth, an improved society and better practices in the business organization. The research study has been undertaken by selecting three tea estates of Jorhat District of Assam, out of the total tea estates 135(Annual Report2013, Published tea Board of India). These tea estates are considered only Company based, tea estates for the study.

This paper is about how Tea Industry performs their Social Responsibility towards their workers. Research is based on the three Tea Gardens industry i.e. how they fulfill their task towards the benefit of Society. In this paper, an attempt has been made to highlights how the companies based tea industries have introduced many workers welfare activities, social development programmes, better working conditions, provide better medical and sanitation facilities, sports and cultural activities in order to improve their standard of living of employees.

Keywords:

Social Responsibility, Welfare activities, CSR, Tea Industry.

1. INTRODUCTION

In corporate sectors as well as organizations, the business principles adopted, cover, business integrity within the organization, health and safety of its employees and the consumer, responsibility towards the environment and social responsibility towards its employees is been performed for the development and welfare of society. Tea Industry is also playing a vital role and giving their contribution towards the benefit of workers by providing various facilities to workers.

The Tea estates have made important strids in family welfare, child immunization, and health tracking and community welfare both in house as well as for the adjoining villages. A forestation and environment protections are key areas which are specially covered and include integrated pest and management systems, effluent treatment and community schemes to enhance awareness of protecting the environment.

It has to be noted that the tea industry serves a number of social, geo-political and environmental issues. Tea gardens essentially employ in its ranks tribes from remote corners of the country, who belong to the socially underprivileged section. The Government's emphasis on social upliftment is more than fulfilled by the tea industry. The gardens also provide subsidized food-grains, housing, quality medical facilities, schooling for children and other long term benefits to the socially challenged sections of the society. Most of the gardens are located in remote areas and tea garden management have been providing micro administration in such far flung areas and have been indirectly helping the state administration in governance.

The Company has ensured that its garden workers have the best possible care and thus have access to Pacca Quarter per family with electricity and water supply, free medical facilities to all workers including medicines, firewood for the purpose of cooking, monthly ration of Tea, protective clothing such as plucking apron, chappals, masks etc. Crèches for the workers children located at convenient points on the estate where the children are cared for and provided milk and rice while their mothers are busy at work. Food grains are provided to families at heavily subsidized rate, well equipped hospitals, maternity clinics, and good schools. The facilities of clubs for both workers and staff have been made available with of certain sports such as Badminton, carom etc. and Television sets for entertainment. Each estate has a number of Primary School depending on the population of the estate and basic education is provided with.

This paper is about how Tea Industry performs their Social Responsibility towards their workers. Research is based on the three Tea Gardens industry namely Kotalgoorie Tea Estate, Kakojan Tea Estate and Hunwal Tea Estate i.e. how they fulfill their task towards the benefit of Society. In this paper, an attempt has been made to highlights how the companies based tea industries have introduced many workers welfare activities, social development programmes, better working conditions, provide better medical and sanitation facilities, sports and cultural activities in order to improve their standard of living of employees.

2. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To study the impacts of the industry on sustainable development.
- To analyze the present roles and responsibility of Tea Industry.

3. PROFILE OF THE STUDY AREA

Kotalgoorie Tea Estate which come under Assam Company India Limited perform social responsibility towards workers welfare activities by providing them - While being engaged in commercial activities, ACL(Assam Company Limited) did not forget their obligation for community development and boost up the socio-economic progression of North East India in general and Assam state in particular. In terms of the social responsibilities, ACL has initiated following activities and is in continuous process of exploring opportunities to uplift social standard of the people living in North East India and protecting the environment and the wild life.

- Contributing to the Economic Growth of North East India.
- Generating employment, revenue & new opportunities of employment.
- Because of direct & indirect growth to the ancillary Industries, Transport etc.
- Inviting Foreign Direct Investment (FDI), collaborating with overseas operators for economic growth.
- Bring in more competitiveness.
- Improving upon quality of Tea production and exploring the discovered Oil fields.
- Encouraging downstream industries for gas consumption and many more industrial growths.

Kakajan Tea Estate which comes under Tata Tea performs their social responsibility towards society. They provide hygienic living conditions, subsidized electricity and rations, schools for their children, handicraft centre for providing vocational training, medical facilities not only to provide basic medical care but also to take care of emergencies with subsidized medicines. There are community areas for hosting entertainment programmes etc. They also have full-fledged hospitals in a couple of gardens with fully equipped operation theatres. The company takes pride in looking after its own people and has set-up facilities to provide better living conditions for its workforce.

And Hunwal Tea Estate comes under Williamson Magor Group .They also perform social responsibilities towards the benefit of society The garden provide subsidized food-grains, housing, quality medical facilities, schooling for children and other long term benefits to the socially challenged sections of the society.

The main aim of the three companies is to increase growth, development, by bringing continuous change, improvement in society through their work and also to raise standard of living of people.

4. METHODOLOGY

The study is conducted through the collection of primary and secondary data. The details are given as follows:

- 4.1. *PRIMARY DATA*: The primary data are collected through questionnaire, personal interviews and observation.

- 4.2. **SECONDARY DATA:** The secondary data are collected from websites, newspaper, reports, handouts, and journals. In addition to this, relevant materials are also collected through the internet as well.
- 4.3. **POPULATION:** The population comprised of male and female residents of Tea Estates in the study area.
- 4.4. **SAMPLE SIZE:** The sample size comprised of 20 respondents from each Tea Estate out of the 100 respondents.
- 4.5. **UNIT OF DATA COLLECTION:** An individual.
- 4.6. **DATA COLLECTION TOOL:** The questionnaire comprised of both close ended and multiple choice questions. The questionnaire was administered personally because it had to be translated into the local language.
- 4.7. **DATA ANALYSIS AND PRESENTATION:** The data has been presented in tabular and graphical form. For the open ended questions, interpretative and descriptive analysis has been done, qualitative and quantitative analysis has been done for open ended and close ended questions respectively.

5. DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

Table: 1.1: Awareness about the Corporate Social Responsibility in the study Area

Sl. No.	Factors	No. of respondent	Percentage
1	Aware	06	10
2	Do not Aware	54	90
Total		60	100

Source: Field Study.

It reveals from the table 1.1 that 90 percent respondent among the three tea estates do not have the awareness regarding the corporate social responsibility while 10 percent of them have the awareness as they are the member of the trade unions. Hence, it is observed that majority of the respondents do not have the awareness due illiteracy.

Table: 1.2: Educational Facilities provided to the students

Sl. No	Factors	No of respondents	Percentage
1	Yes	03	05
2	No	57	95
		60	100

Source: Field Study.

It can be concluded from the above table 1.2 that 95 percent respondent among the three tea estates do not have awareness about the educational facilities provided to the students while only 5 percent of them have awareness about this.

Table: 1.3: Training Camps held for benefit of the beneficiaries.

Sl. No	Factors	No of respondents	Percentage
1	Yes	12	20
2	No	48	80
Total		60	100

Source: Field Study

It reveals above the table 1.3 that 80 percent of the beneficiaries are not aware about the training camp which are held for their benefit. Among them only 20 percent have aware of the training camps.

Table: 1.4: Donations provided for the improvement of the society

Sl. No	Factors	No of Respondents	Percentage
1	Yes	24	40
2	No	36	60
Total		60	100

Source: Field Study.

It has been concluded from the table 1.4 that 60 percent of the tea populations among the three tea estates do not know about the donations which are provided for the improvement of the society. Among the total population only 40 percent of them are aware about the donations provided for the improvement of the society.

6. MAJOR FINDINGS

1. 90 percent respondents among the three tea estates do not have the awareness regarding the corporate social responsibility while 10 percent of them have the awareness as they are the member of the trade unions.
2. 95 percent respondent among the three tea estates do not have awareness about the educational facilities provided to the students.
3. 80 percent of the beneficiaries are not aware about the training camps which are held for their benefit.
4. 60 percent of the tea populations among the three tea estates do not know about the donations which are provided for the improvement of the society.

7. SUGGESTIONS

1. The State Government along with the others social organizations should made the tea Companies mandatory to do some social welfare works for the better development of the society in the heads of corporate social responsibility. The Tea Companies should be displayed all the social welfare works in the general notice board so that all the people of the gardens awareness about the development works of the Companies.
2. The Tea Estates should arrange some classes, give demos or training programs for all such facilities which they are providing to the working as well as non-working people of their gardens so that the peoples can be aware and enjoy their benefits which are specially designed for them.

8. CONCLUSION

It can be concluded from the study that Tea Industry is also playing a vital role and giving their contribution towards the benefit of workers by providing various facilities to them. But the major problems which are found in the study is that the workers or other people of the tea gardens are unaware about the benefit which they should get. As many of them do not have any knowledge or are not aware of about the welfare programs, facilities that are provided to them from the tea gardens. It is necessary for the Tea Companies to take some steps so that all can enjoy the benefits and improve their standard of living.

9. REFERENCES

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